

“THE IMPACT OF ENCLAVES AND EXCLAVES ON INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS”**Oripov Bahodir Olimjon o‘g‘li**

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Abstract: This article examines the influence of enclave and exclave territories on international relations, their historical formation, and geopolitical significance. Particular attention is given to the role of enclave territories in Central Asia in border, transport, economic, and diplomatic relations. The article also analyzes the political and social problems arising in enclave and exclave regions, as well as possible ways to resolve them. In addition, the importance of international law in regulating territorial disputes is highlighted.

Keywords: enclave, exclave, international relations, geopolitics, border issues, Central Asia, diplomatic relations, territorial conflicts, international law, regional security, geoeconomics.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние анклавных и эксклавных территорий на международные отношения, их историческое формирование и геополитическое значение. Особое внимание уделяется роли анклавных территорий Центральной Азии в пограничных, транспортных, экономических и дипломатических отношениях. Также анализируются политические и социальные проблемы, возникающие в анклавных и эксклавных регионах, а также пути их решения. Кроме того, раскрывается значение международного права в урегулировании территориальных споров.

Ключевые слова: анклав, эксклав, международные отношения, геополитика, пограничные проблемы, Центральная Азия, дипломатические отношения, территориальные конфликты, международное право, региональная безопасность, геоэкономика.

Introduction.

Today, territorial issues occupy an important place in international relations among states. In particular, problems related to enclave and exclave territories directly affect diplomatic relations not only politically, but also economically and culturally. Since enclave and exclave territories are either surrounded by the territory of another state or separated from the main territory of their parent state, they are considered unique geopolitical regions in international relations. In some cases, such territories strengthen cooperation between states, while in others they become a cause of border disputes and conflicts. Among these issues, problems related to water resources, transport routes, land disputes, and border control significantly influence interstate relations. Therefore, studying enclave and exclave territories from historical-geographical and geopolitical perspectives is of great importance.

Research Methodology and Literature Review

During the preparation of this article, scientific literature, articles, academic journals, and internet sources were used. Throughout the research, the role of enclave and exclave territories in international relations was analyzed from political, economic, and geopolitical perspectives. In addition, the scientific works of local and foreign scholars were used as the main sources in studying the problems related to enclave territories in Central Asia. In the process of analyzing the literature, the historical formation of enclave and exclave territories, border issues, their place in international law, and their influence on diplomatic relations between states were scientifically examined. Comparative analysis, historical approach, and scientific observation methods were applied during the research.

Main Part

After the establishment of the USSR, the real situation in Central Asia, a significant part of which was included in the Turkestan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic before national-territorial delimitation, was characterized by K. Atabaev, a member of the Central Executive Committee of the

USSR. At the second session of the second convocation in 1924, he stated: “The activities of the Soviet government in Turkestan constantly faced friction, which hindered most productive work. Economic activities carried out within the environment of one nation were often directed against another, intensifying conflicts and creating extremely complex national combinations promoted by one group in opposition to another” [1:36]. As a result, territorial delimitation was carried out while formally considering the interests of the majority population, yet these borders eventually became the cause of numerous economic and political conflicts in the region.

The issue of enclave and exclave territories in Central Asia has been studied by various scholars during the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, including Soviet, local, and Western researchers. Among Soviet scholars, B. V. Lunin conducted research on territorial issues in Central Asia during the Soviet period, including enclaves and exclaves. S. G. Agajanov wrote scientific works on the historical and geographical issues of Central Asia and territorial borders. Among Western scholars, international law expert Rein Müllerson carried out research on territorial issues in Central Asia, including enclaves and exclaves. French scholar Olivier Roy, a specialist in Central Asia and the Islamic world, studied ethnic and territorial issues in the region. Regarding the historical background of the situation in the Fergana Valley, the studies of Frederick Starr are noteworthy. Local scholars such as Sh. Jumaxanov, A. Toshpo‘latov, Sh. Saidov, S. Alamanov, and A. Koychuev have also written scientific works, articles, and books on this topic [2:19]. In particular, during the study of territories in Central Asia, the mechanisms of national-territorial delimitation are widely discussed. Furthermore, examining the contributions of the above-mentioned scholars to the origins of territorial issues related to enclaves and exclaves is important for understanding their historical formation from both geographical and historical perspectives.

In international relations, agreements are studied not only on the basis of peace and mutual understanding between states, but also in connection with natural resources and irrigation facilities belonging to those states. In particular, researchers examining the international nature of relations also study the historical processes within the internal territories of states as well as their borders.

Over the past years and months, conflicts that have occurred along the borders and border regions of Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Tajikistan have made it possible to describe the current situation as unstable. Statements by state leaders expressing their readiness to complete the legal formalization of state borders, as well as certain practical measures that have been implemented, have not been sufficient to ease tensions between border populations and border services. The acute shortage of natural resources necessary for enclave populations — including arable land, pastures, forests, hayfields, water, and fuel — continues to remain the main factor behind ethno-territorial conflicts among local communities. This situation is becoming even more complicated due to the rapid population growth in enclave territories [3:458]. Primarily, because of the increasing study of such enclave and exclave territories in international relations, even geographically isolated regions have gradually begun to develop, while issues related to territorial economic cooperation have also become subjects of various discussions. As a result, enclave and exclave territories have started to occupy an important place in interstate politics.

From the perspective of international law, territorial issues are of great importance in preventing disputes between states. At the same time, in certain cases, territorial problems themselves become a cause of interstate conflicts. Usually, territorial disagreements arise as a result of opposing views of states regarding ownership of a particular territory. International law is considered one of the most effective mechanisms for resolving such disputes peacefully and ensuring territorial security. State borders are formed on the basis of political, geographical, economic, and ethnic factors. Therefore, the norms of international law recognize and protect the sovereignty of states over their territories. Borders constitute an important component of the system of international relations and serve to ensure peaceful

coexistence and cooperation among states. The experience of the Central Asian states demonstrates that issues related to enclave and exclave territories continue to hold significant importance in regional security and diplomatic relations today [4:29–30]. Furthermore, due to the frequent occurrence of conflicts, ethnic, religious, and cultural tensions and conflict-oriented ideologies often emerge among the population.

Most of the enclaves that form this “geopolitical archipelago” are relatively small in territorial size; therefore, they are usually administered as part of larger administrative units. However, in some cases, if the enclave territory is larger, it may be governed at the district or municipal level. There are also large enclaves covering hundreds of kilometers. One example is the Alaska semi-enclave. This territory of the United States covers more than 1.7 million square kilometers. Nevertheless, such vast territories are generally characteristic of isolated enclaves [5:1143]. In general, specialists have studied numerous sources and academic works concerning the geographical location and development of enclaves. Therefore, within the international sphere, such territories continue to possess significant relevance due to their conflict-prone nature, where economic and political interests occupy a central role.

In this regard, E. Y. Vinokurov proposed three theoretical criteria. The first is the location of the state capital, the second is the relative size of the territory, and the third is the relative size of the population. In practice, according to the norms of international law, regardless of population size or territorial extent, the territory where the capital is located is considered the main territory of the state. The primary reason for this is that the center of state authority is concentrated there. As mentioned above, such cases are relatively rare in determining territorial status. For example, when Pakistan was established in 1947, the territory of East Bengal, where more than half of the population lived, was considered an exclave of Pakistan until 1971. After the declaration of independence of Bangladesh in 1971, this territory became an independent state. Since the capital and the main administrative center of the country were located in the western part, West Pakistan was regarded as the principal territory of the state [6:42].

The development and socio-economic life of enclave territories are often dependent on the state surrounding them. If the surrounding state restricts free access to and from the enclave, life in such a territory may become almost comparable to conditions in a prison. For example, Shohimardon is a territory of Uzbekistan, but it is an enclave located within the territory of Kyrgyzstan. Due to border problems between the two states, entry to and exit from this territory remained difficult for many years. As a result, carrying out export-import relations also became complicated [7:10–11]. In this regard, it can be said that when compared with one another, the enclaves located in Central Asia differ considerably from European enclaves. Issues such as state border security, the interaction of ethnic and religious matters within the region, and diplomatic international relations with neighboring territories play an important role in this difference.

Despite the existence of certain border markers, they are difficult to locate because many of them are hidden among bushes or situated along roadsides. Most importantly, no special inspections have been introduced for individuals traveling from the SBA territories to the Republic’s territory, since the United Kingdom guaranteed the implementation of such control at the external borders of the SBA. Therefore, people living or working in exclave territories are able to move freely within the military base area. Only certain restricted zones, such as military facilities, are prohibited from entry. In practice, the borders between the exclaves and the SBA have almost no impact on the daily lives of local residents. For example, it is possible to travel by car from Ormidhia to Xylotymbou without any obstacles or official formalities. The same procedure also applies to tourists and SBA personnel [8:9–10]. In my opinion, the openness of borders in exclave territories is highly beneficial for the population

because people can move from one territory to another without unnecessary difficulties. This demonstrates the importance of good-neighborly relations between states.

The study of enclaves is important because the populations living in such territories often face political and economic difficulties. Since they are separated from the main territory of the state, problems arise in administration, security, and economic relations. In addition, enclaves and exclaves strongly influence relations between the parent state and the state surrounding them. Although their territorial size may be small, they represent an important geopolitical factor in international relations. In some cases, such territories may become a source of disputes between states. For example, Gibraltar has long remained a political issue for Spain, while Ceuta and Melilla continue to be persistent political concerns for Morocco [9:3–4]. In particular, within international relations, the large or small size of enclave and exclave territories can create difficulties during detailed territorial studies and border delimitation processes. In general, the close geographical location of enclave and exclave territories within neighboring states can also strengthen friendly and stable relations in international affairs.

Diplomatic missions, such as embassies and consulates, as well as military bases, are exempt from the jurisdiction of the receiving state. In other words, the laws of the host country where the embassy is located generally do not apply within the territory of the embassy or the military base itself. This exemption from the jurisdiction of the receiving country is defined as extraterritoriality. However, places and buildings that enjoy certain forms of extraterritoriality are not considered true enclaves, because in all cases the host state retains full sovereignty. In addition to embassies, some other areas also possess limited forms of extraterritoriality [10]. State institutions therefore play an important role in separated territories. For this reason, in enclaves and exclaves, mutual respect in relations is especially significant, while the alignment of interstate interests remains an important factor for future cooperation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, enclave and exclave territories are considered one of the important geopolitical factors in international relations. Such territories strongly influence political, economic, and diplomatic relations between states. In particular, in the enclave regions of Central Asia, various conflicts frequently arise due to issues related to borders, water resources, land, and transportation. At the same time, if good-neighborly relations and cooperation exist between states, enclave territories can become not a source of conflict, but rather a connecting factor. Research demonstrates that the development of enclave and exclave territories largely depends on the policies pursued with neighboring states. Open borders, freedom of movement, and the development of economic relations contribute to improving the living standards of the populations living in these territories. Conversely, political disagreements and border disputes intensify socio-economic difficulties within such regions.

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